

Particle Futures: Mineral Insulated Cable in High Energy Physics and Radiation Environments

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Abstract— "Mineral Insulated Cable" by the very design provides an ideal mechanism to handle high intensity magnetic fields in particle accelerator applications while withstanding the considerable exposure to radiation environments.

INTRODUCTION

Mineral insulated cable (aka MI Cable) has been used for over 70 years in numerous commercial, industrial, and scientific applications due to its properties of being able to handle high temperatures, high voltages and radiation conditions. It was initially presented in the 1930's but was advanced commercially in the early 1950s, in the UK, for use in the oil and gas industry, but has since found its way into many other applications, including particle accelerators and charged particle environments like nuclear reactors. .

Particle accelerators use high level electromagnetic fields to accelerate and direct charged particles, such as electrons or protons, to very high velocities. The magnetic fields supplied for this process are generated by powerful superconducting magnets, which need a special type of cable that can handle high currents and large magnetic fields without overheating or producing unwanted magnetic fields.

II. MI CABLE

MI Cable is an ideal fit for this application due to its ability to operate in considerable high temperatures and intense magnetic fields. The cable is constructed of a copper, or copper alloy, conductor surrounded by a magnesium oxide insulation (MgO), which is then encompassed by a metal sheath, made of Austenitic Stainless Steel, Inconel grades or Copper. The insulation provides a high degree of thermal conductivity at high temperatures, allowing the cable to dissipate heat generated by the high currents without dangerously overheating. Additionally, the metal sheath provides a high degree of electromagnetic shielding, which helps to prevent unwanted magnetic fields from interfering with the particle beam quality and control.

III. ADVANTAGES

Key advantages of MI Cable in particle accelerators is its ability to handle intense magnetic fields without producing significant magnetic interference.

This is critical in particle accelerator applications, where even small generated magnetic fields can have a significant impact on the trajectory of the fired particle beam. MI Cable can be manufactured to tight tolerances, allowing it to be engineering designed to specific applications with high precision.

IV. RADIATION

Particle accelerator technology is opening up the universe to modern physics, with the opportunity to prove various theories

However, this comes at a price of ever higher energy envelopes and particle beam intensities. Cable engineering in this environment results in a number of possible cable insulation materials both organic (polymers) and inorganic (minerals, glass, ceramics). Conventional cable insulations (organic) used for magnetic coil cable designs have shown a estimate radiation life of 10^7 Gy (1), which limits the operational efficiency of these products. When dealing with both high temperature and high radiation inorganic MI cable is typically used. (2)

Magnesium oxide (MgO) an inorganic mineral insulation is used in most MI Cable constructions. (Silicon Dioxide (SiO₂) is used in certain applications due to it's light weight status in avionics systems). The exposure levels of Magnesium Oxide (MgO) approach 10^8 Gy with little potential damage, and just over 10^9 with some potential damage considerations (1). There are few inorganic materials beyond this operational range, one being quartz at 10^{10} Gy radiation resistance.

V. CONFIGURATION

Literature review reflects two dominate configurations in Mineral Insulated cable (MI) design for particle accelerator magnetic coils.

(1) Square Hollow Core

The MI cable is constructed in a square orientation for coil packing purposes with a likewise hollow square center for flow of cooling agent (water) to control temperature generated due to the high current densities required for the field. The outer section has a copper or alloy sheath, with Magnesium Oxide (MgO) layer, then a copper hollow core. The engineered material thicknesses are reflective of the voltage and current loading, along with NRTL minimum design standards. This

cooling core configuration is common in the industry in other cable constructions beyond MI cable.

Square Hollow Core Figure

(2) Square Solid Core

The MI cable is constructed in a square orientation for coil packing purposes with a likewise solid square center. The outer section has a copper or alloy sheath, with Magnesium Oxide (MgO) layer, then a copper hollow core. The engineered material thicknesses are reflective of the voltage and current loading, along with NRTL minimum design standards. Unlike the Square Hollow Core conventional design, the Square Solid Core takes advantage of the thermal conductivity factors involved with copper and a highly compacted Magnesium Oxide (MgO), which allows a high heat transfer condition through the cable construction to external heat sinks, while maintaining high current densities in the cable.(3)

Square Solid Core Figure

VI. CONCLUSION

The use of Mineral Insulated Cable (MI) for Particle Accelerator applications provides a safe and effective means of providing the high currents and temperature exposure required for the generation of intense magnetic fields. It also introduces a high level of radiation resistance not found in organic based cable construction methods. With new and larger accelerator systems coming on line in the 2020's thru 2030's the continued use of Mineral Insulated (magnesium oxide) Cables will continue well into the future.

- (1) CERN 82-05 Super Proton Synchrotron Division June 4th, 1982 "Radiation-Resistant Magnets" CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research – RL. Keizer and M. Mottier -1982
- (2) NUREG/CR-6384_BNL-NUREG-52480 "Literature Review of Environmental Qualifications of Safety Related Electrical Cables" Brookhaven National Laboratory – M. Subudhi - 1996
- (3) "Mineral Insulated Conductors for Magnetic Coils" Los Alamos National Laboratory – A. Harvey – 1970
- (4) SLAC-PUB-4910 Stanford University "Radiation Hardening of Magnet Coils" Stanford Linear Accelerator Center – A. Harvey – 1989
- (5) CERN Geneva, Switzerland "Dielectric Insulation and High Voltage Issues" – D. Tommasini